

**PREVALENCE OF MALARIA AMONG PATIENTS WITH DIFFERENT BLOOD
GROUPS ATTENDING GENERAL HOSPITAL KATSINA**

BY

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**BEING A PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF BIOLOGICAL
SCIENCES, COLLEGE OF NATURAL AND APPLIED SCIENCES, ALQALAM
UNIVERSITY KATSINA IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS
FOR THE AWARD OF BACHELOR OF SCIENCE DEGREE (B.Sc.) IN BIOLOGY**

FEBRUARY 2022

DECLARATION

"I hereby declared that this work titled **“THE PREVALENCE OF MALARIA AMONG PATIENTS WITH DIFFERENT BLOOD GROUPS ATTENDING GENERAL HOSPITAL KATSINA”** is the product of my own research efforts, undertaken under the supervision of Mal. Abdullahi Shehu Ado and has not been presented and will not be presented elsewhere for the award of degree or certificate. All sources have been duly acknowledged.

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this work titled “**THE PREVALENCE OF MALARIA AMONG PATIENTS WITH DIFFERENT BLOOD GROUPS ATTENDING GENERAL HOSPITAL KATSINA.**” by Musa Abubakar Ibrahim (NAS/BIO/18/2057) was carried out under my supervision.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

In the name of Allah the most gracious the most compassionate, all praise be to Allah the lord of the universe who gave me the golden opportunity to present this report. May the peace and blessings of Allah be upon his beloved Messenger prophet Muhammad (SAW).

My appreciation and gratitude goes to my parents, for their support and prayers. Thanks for teaching me to learn and to know and understand myself. May Allah reward them abundantly for their tireless prayers and advice to achievement of my goals

And I would like to express my deep and sincere gratitude to my supervisor in the person of Mal. Abdullahi Shehu Ado for his extraordinary support.

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to my beloved parents May Allah (S.W.T) Reward them *with Jannatul Firdausi* for their support, love and prayers.

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to investigate ABO blood groups association with malaria parasitemia among patients attending General Hospital Katsina. Two millilitres (2ml) of venous blood was collected by venepuncture using 5ml syringes from symptomatic malaria patients between October and December 2021. Blood samples were immediately dispensed into Ethylene Diamine Tetra-acid (EDTA) anticoagulated containers and mixed appropriately. ABO blood typing using Antisera A, B, D was carried out on samples. The malaria plasmodium falciparum Rapid Test Device (whole blood) package insert kit was used to test for the presence of malaria parasites in the specimens. Analyzed total number of 100 blood samples made up of 20(20.00%) A Positive and 3(3.00%) A Negative, B Positive 25 (25.00%) and 1 (1.00%) B Negative, AB Positive 12 (12.00%) and 3 (3.00%) AB Negative and O Positive 34(34.00%) and O Negative of 2 (2.00%). Malaria parasitaemia seemed to be relatively high across all blood groups with group B and AB apparently recorded the highest and the least infection rates respectively. There was no statistical significance in the prevalence of malaria parasitaemia among A B O blood groups of patients attending General Hospital Katsina ($p>0.05$) and between malaria parasitaemia severity and ABO blood groups of patients ($p>0.05$).

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Malaria is caused by a plasmodium parasite that spends its life in both humans and certain species of mosquitoes, four species of plasmodium that cause malaria in humans; are *Plasmodium falciparum*, *Plasmodium vivax*, *Plasmodium malariae*, and *Plasmodium ovale*. Of these, *Plasmodium falciparum* is the most important in most parts of the tropics and is responsible for most severe illnesses and deaths. Malaria may have reached its maximum world dissemination between 1855 when it was found in southern Canada and 1922-1923 when it touched the arctic cycle in Russia. Presently, the disease ranks first in terms of morbidity and mortality worldwide. The genus plasmodium has been found in man and mammals (Gilles 2017). Despite the high morbidity and mortality, certain individuals are resistant to malaria infection due to different immune responses by the host and to a varying extent, and certain characteristics possessing protective value against infection such as A B O blood group type, of available evidence suggests that the origin, distribution and relative proportion of ABO blood sickle cell trait (HBAS) and sickle cell disease (HBSS) (Otajevwo, 2013). The association of genetic markers with man has been the subject of numerous investigations since the protection afforded by sickle-cell haemoglobin against infection by the *falciparum* malaria parasite. Broad range groups in humans may have been directly selective genetic pressure from plasmodium *falciparum* infection. Clinical reports of ABO blood groups and *plasmodium falciparum* infection reveal a correlation between disease severity and ABO groups (WHO, 2018).

However, several studies undertaken have been unable to link ABO blood groups to the incidence of malaria or the repeated attacks of malaria. Recent studies of the pathogenesis of malaria have shown that parasites triggered red blood cell rosette formation associated with the severity of clinical disease and malaria. Rosetting was established as a *plasmodium falciparum* virulence factor, the expression of which is modified by host factors. Anti-Ro setting activity,

presumably mediated by antibodies, was found in sera from patients in malaria-endemic areas, and it was demonstrated that such activity was more abundant in individuals with uncomplicated malaria than in those with the cerebral disease, suggesting that humoral immunity protects against rosette formation in vivo. Erythrocytes from individuals with sickle-cell trait, A-and B-thalassemia trait or with HBE formed smaller and weaker rosettes than did normal HBAA red blood cells. Recently even *Plasmodium vivax* infection has been reported with clinical severity. There is a paucity of hospital-based, comparative studies to investigate the relationship between blood group types and the severity of malaria infections. This study was undertaken to fill up the lacunae in understanding the relationship between different blood group phenotypes and malaria in a hospital environment (WHO/Malaria Association, 2010).

Plasmodium is a tiny single parasite that infects the cell. Human malaria is caused by four species of plasmodium parasite which are mentioned above, the four species causing human malaria differ morphologically, immunologically, geographical distribution relapse pattern and in drug response. *Plasmodium falciparum* causes serious disease, *P. vivax* as most common and infection are rarely fatal, *Plasmodium ovale* which is restricted to West Africa also produce mild illness and *Plasmodium malariae* in isolated places scattered across the globe which causes severe fever but not life threatening species of plasmodium are also found in primates, rodents, rats and mammals, birds and reptiles.

The genome of *Plasmodium falciparum* has been sequenced by an international consortium. The genome consisted of 23 million base pairs of deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA), split over 14 chromosomes (the human genome has 3 billion base pairs). The freely available genome information is already helping researchers develop new anti-malarial drugs, whereas some produced and more are to be produced. Malaria is most commonly transmitted by 400 species throughout the world, only about 60 are vectors of malaria under natural conditions, some 30 mosquitoes, although, only a minority feed on human blood. Only female mosquitoes drink

blood usually to feed the production of their eggs. Female mosquito bites usually during or between sunrise and sunset (Gilles 2017).

When an infected mosquito bites to suck blood, parasites infect the liver cells. The classic clinical causes of malaria consist of fever that coincides with the parasites bursting out of the red blood cells (RBCs). Infected Red Blood Cells can also clump together, blocking blood flow and damaging internal organs including the brain. Variation in some human genes (such as those that cause sickle-cell anaemia or thalassemia) reduces the incidence of malaria. The basis of this research is to examine the incidence of the patient with different blood groups to the infection of various malaria parasites that exist since the blood group is one of the genetic changes seen in man that can confer a greater or lesser degree of resistance to malaria (Doffing blood groups).

Plasmodium falciparum malaria is a known cause of morbidity and mortality, especially in children of Sub-Saharan Africa the clinical outcome of *falciparum* malaria in endemic areas is, among other factors, associated with erythrocyte polymorphisms Including the ABO blood groups. ABO blood group refers to a system of carbohydrate antigens expressed on human erythrocytes and other human cells. The “A” and “B” antigens on erythrocytes are disaccharides All erythrocytes possess an “H” disaccharide on their surfaces (except the rare Bombay phenotype, which has no ABO antigens) Individuals with blood groups “A” and “B” have the “A” and “B” antigens, respectively, together with the “H” antigen. Blood group “AB” individuals have both “A” and “B” antigens together with the “H.” Blood group “O” individuals, however, have neither “A” nor “B” antigens but “H.” Numerous associations have been reported between the ABO blood group system and some disease conditions such as skin cancer *schistosomiasis onchocerciasis* and HIV infection There are also reports on the association of ABO blood group with susceptibility, resistance, and severity of *P. falciparum* malaria infection Individuals with blood group “A” have been found to be highly susceptible to *falciparum* malaria whereas blood group “O” is said to confer protection against complicated cases Low

parasitaemia and uncomplicated *P. falciparum* malaria cases among blood group “O” individuals have been observed. These differences in susceptibility and severity of *P. falciparum* malaria infection among the “A,” “B,” “AB,” (Hindawi, 2016).

1.1. AIM

The aim of this study is to assess the prevalence of malaria among patients with different blood groups attending General Hospital Katsina.

OBJECTIVES:

The objectives of this study are:

1. To determine the relative abundance of malaria parasites among different blood groups in the patients attending General Hospital Katsina
2. To determine the malaria parasite count in four different blood groups of patients attending General Hospital Katsina

1.2. STATEMENT OF RESEARCH PROBLEMS

1. There is no prevalence of malaria infection in different blood groups
2. The level of malaria count associated with a specific blood group

JUSTIFICATION

The knowledge of this research will help in reducing infant mortality and death in patients and this will, in turn, reduce the incidence of malaria infection in different blood groups in General Hospital Katsina State and Nigeria as a whole. This project will provide useful information and data on the incidence of malaria infection which will serve as a basis for helping health personnel in looking for the possible solution to eradicate this disease.

Also include hypothesis as 1.4

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

The earliest description of what has been malaria as a disease was prepared by ``emperor Huang`` around (2700BC). The first bacteriologist classified the fever known to be malaria but his teachings were neglected and ignored for 2000 years. However human malaria is a disease that is distributed worldwide by a protozoan of the genus plasmodium in part of Africa, Asia, and South America where the environmental condition has stagnant water for mosquitoes close contact of the arthropod vector and man, breed temperature, humidity and presence of certain plants where mosquitoes may breed. Some animal species which aggravate malaria infection use the blood-feeding habit of some Anopheles mosquitoes thereby diverting the attention of man and consequently reducing the entire rate of transmission. Moreover, the respective biological, environmental and occupational habits and many-sided activities of the human population produce a condition of social and economic environment that often have a desirable effect on the amount and degree of malarial transmission. Man being the one and only important vertebrate host of human malaria and exercise a very great influence on the epidemiology of malaria. ``Sydenham`` (1624-89BC) refocused attention on Hippocrates' methods, he again classified the fevers of malaria and demonstrated that perving bark ``afforded the surest hope of treating intermittent fever effectively`` when a repeated dose is being given four-hourly Charles Louis Alphonse Laveran (1845-1922) a French army, surgeon was the first person to recognize malaria parasites in human in the 1880s Golgi (1843-1916) deduced that the different malaria parasites are: *Plasmodium falciparum*, *P. ovale*, *P. malariae* and *P. vivax* were later identified by two other Italian malariologists March Falla and Bignami. ``Pam and Graz`` (2017), stated that malaria is most prevalent in rural areas and is generally associated with agricultural occupation. Certain activities of man indirectly create ideal breeding sites for the mosquitoes thereby aiding greater man-vector contact and hence increasing the transmission of malaria. Malaria can also be

transmitted through blood transfusion from an infected individual and through the route of transplantation. ``*Plasmodium falciparum*'' one of the most spread species of malaria parasite in tropical Africa is the most virulent and the one which enjoys the reputation as the greatest killer of mankind. Finally, deliberate injection in malaria therapy ``Hall'' (2016), the four species or features of the various stages, the duration of each development phase, the pathological effects and the staining of the parasites are associated with the changes in the Red Blood Cells (RBCs) ``Soulsby'' (2016).

2.1 TYPES OF PLASMODIUM PARASITES

(a) *P. falciparum*: this species is responsible for the malignant form of malaria infection. In the synchrony of schizogony of the parasite within the erythrocytes, *Plasmodium falciparum* seems to be the on exo-erythrocytic cycle therefore, all the merozoites are been discharged into the bloodstream at ago. It is characterized by attack after 48hours interval once adequately treated relapse does not occur, it could prove fatal because it is the commonest species in Nigeria.

(b) *P. vivax*: this species of plasmodium is usually responsible for being tertian malaria (sudden fever) the species causes malarial attacks which occur at cyclical intervals (48 hours). The Red Blood Cells (RBCs) becomes enlarged decoloured and develop a stippled appearance due to the presence of a number of dots usually known as schuffries dots, elapses commonly occur several minutes after the first attack.

(c) *P. ovale*: this is another species of plasmodium which is very much similar to *P. vivax* in terms of action it is responsible for being tertian malaria and cyclical attack after every 48 hours (2 days). In ovale, the Red Blood Cells (RBCs) are larger and more numerous and brighter red in colour.

(d) *P. Malariae*: this species is quite responsible for quarter malaria, the red cells are only jointly stippled but rather as cleft or knobs which is characterized by an attack after every 72 hours

intervals of incubation periods where relapse may occur after many months of adequate treatment of the first attack.

2.2 LIFE CYCLE OF MALARIA PARASITE:

Figure 2.2: The complete cycle of malaria parasite (plasmodium) which infect human beings are in two (2) phases viz: Malaria no more, United Kingdom. (2014)

- (a) Sporogony (a period of development within the mosquito).
- (b) Schizogony (a period of infection in man).

The vector phase of the cycle (Sporogony): the known female anopheles mosquito becomes infected when it feeds on human blood containing gametocytes, the sexual form of the parasites, the male and female gametocytes unite and penetrate the stomach wall and form an oocyst (zygote). After 10-14 days, the sporozoites are then liberated from the oocyst and migrate to the salivary gland of the mosquito which takes a blood meal from its susceptible victim.

The human phase of the cycle (schizogony): Human, being the host of this second phase of the cycle; when an infected anopheles mosquito bites the human being, it infects the plasmodium in the form of sporozoites into the bloodstream within 30 minutes, the sporozoites disappear from the bloodstream and enters the parenchymal cell of the liver where the pre-erythrocyte stage of the development takes place. However, after about 7-9 days, numerous merozoites are liberated from the liver and enter the circulating erythrocytes (except in *p. falciparum* infection). Or they may enter new liver cells where they will be responsible for the relapse which are characteristics of malaria infection. In the erythrocytes, the merozoites develop from the sexual reproduction into schizonts from which new batches of daughter merozoites are liberated into the bloodstream on rupture of the parasitized erythrocytes. More so, each merozoite may enter a new red blood cell (RBC) and several cycles of schizogony usually occur and develops, this time schizonts get into the male and female gametocytes which when circulating the bloodstream may be injected by the anopheles mosquito while seeking a blood meal from the infected person

2.3 MODE OF TRANSMISSION:

Different mosquito species vary from one region to the other, the difference between these species can be dramatic, for instance, some species of mosquitoes never bite humans, others prefer birds or domestic animals, certain species

Prefer to take blood during the daytime while others at night.

Mosquitoes that feed on human blood also differ in their feeding and resting behaviour after feeding, resulting in a different response to residual insecticide. The blood sucking habit of female mosquitoes makes them to be endophagic or exophagic as well as endophilic and endophagic or pedophilic and exophagic. This behaviour makes it possible for the female mosquitoes to transmit diseases. The endophilic and endophagic mosquitoes constitute the bulk of diseases transmission (Awolola *et al*, 2013) hence knowledge of the resting behaviour of different mosquito species is of paramount importance in developing control strategy.

Plasmodium falciparum is one of the most widely spread species of malaria parasite exclusively between man and the vector (mosquito) which happens to be the intermediate host. The main factor which influences the epidemiology of malaria is the intensity of transmission and the immune response of the infected persons (Afolayan and Adeyemi, 2019). Man being the intermediate host of the malaria parasite, the transmission in man may be stable and unstable malaria.

i. Stable malaria: in the areas where malaria transmission occurs for at least six (6) months in a year and is intense, children suffer repeated attacks from the age of a few months. When immunity is established, patients may still suffer attacks of malaria but these are comparatively mild and last for only a few days. Older people are lately affected. There is still variation in the incidence of malaria from year to year, although there may be marked seasonal fluctuation, particularly in children (Afoayan and Adeyemi, 2019).

ii. Unstable malaria: in the areas where malaria transmission is unstable there are marked changes in transmission from one season to another and from one year to another. The seasonal transmission is short and infection of any individuals is comparatively in-frequent so, that immunity is, therefore, unstable to reach high level, when an outbreak of malaria occurs, it follows the explosive breeding of mosquitoes, it does so in the form of an epidemic with people of all areas of unstable transmission (Afoayan and Adeyemi, 2019).

2.4 CLINICAL SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS:

The characteristic features of malaria fever occur usually in different stages via; the cold stage (Righerghill), hot stage (high fever) and the sweating stage (defervescence).

- a. The cold stage (Righerghill): this is characterized by headache; rigour etc, the patient feels cold and shivers even though his temperature is rising.
- b. The hot stage (High fever): this is the stage where the patient's temperature rises to its peak, a pain in the joints and back and often ``vomiting with diarrhoea'' in some patients.
- c. The sweating stage (defervescence): in this stage, the patient perspires, the temperature falls and the headache, as well as other pain, is revived until the next rigour (severe).

Other symptoms include backache, postural hypertension and common physical signs such as anaemia, mild jaundice, and moderate fender enlargement of the spleen suggest the diagnosis, other main malaria abnormalities in routine laboratory investigations. In complicated malaria, evidence of hemolytic anaemia, resulting from granulocytes and lymphocytes, thrombocytopenia minimal albuminuria (Cheese borough, 2012).

2.5 THE PATHOLOGY OF MALARIA

The study has conformed to the previous belief that malaria play a role in the etiopathogenesis of persistent splenomegaly in sickle cell patients in a fashion similar to but not suit the same as in tropical splenomegaly syndrome of malaria infection, the spleen has been shown to modulate parasite antigen expression on the surface of infected erythrocytes and effect of the process include cytoadherence, which is central to the pathophysiology of several *falciparum* malaria and related phenomenon of rhesus formation of *Plasmodium falciparum* if infected erythrocytes cycle in vitro and the recent result shows that five of the ten cases of pulmonary involvement with *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria showed no evidence of all cases were treated with oxygen and positive expiratory pressure.

2.6 COMPLICATION OF MALARIA

A serious complication of malaria occurs primarily in falciparum infection, particularly in children and women who have experienced repeated attacks within an adequate treatment. The complications include;

- Anaemia
- Coma
- Respiratory distress
- Hyperpyrexia
- Nephritic
- General malaria
- Abortion in early pregnancy
- Gastro-intestinal malaria
- Neurological disorder
- Algid malaria

The clinical features of severe malaria are the first three mentions above; these can be seen as resulting from the interaction of the main three components mentioned above earlier said. This severe anaemia may result in parasitic growth and Red Blood Cells (RBCs) destruction. It reduces oxygen delivery to tissues caused by combination and exacerbated by reducing oxygen-carrying capacity due to anaemia which leads to a profound metabolic acidosis 'where the blood tissues become too acidic' in turn, it leads to respiratory distress, a compensatory mechanism by which the patient breath harder to try to blow off carbon-dioxide in order to reduce the acidity content. The most well-known and feared manifestation of malaria in which patients go into comas and often have convulsions. In some cases, coma shows that the body is responding to overwhelming metabolic disturbances, particularly the metabolic acidosis described above. But massive packing of blood vessels by infected parasites leads to a variety of local effects including

tissue damages, cytokines activation and other poorly understood cellular pathology. Black water fever, which is also a situation whereby malaria attacks the ‘malignant’ that is a large number of Red Blood Cells are also destroyed, the haemoglobin from the Red Blood Capsules is excreted in the urine, which is dark and almost of cola colour. However, the enlargement of the spleen may occur for days or weeks (Cheese borough, 2012).

2.7 IMMUNITY TO MALARIA

Immunity to malaria always develops over several years of continuous exposure and infection. It is therefore characterized by a gradual decrease in frequency and severity of the clinical disease. Repetitive works of various antigenic may account for this gradual onset of immunity. Recent work has elucidated more about the nature of immunity; the trigger for immune response is the release of parasite molecules in the bloodstream when malaria-infected the RBCs and ruptures it. These foreign materials activate macrophages, the cells that play an important role in killing the bacteria or some bacteria, protozoa and tumour cells of the immune system and presenting the foreign antigens to the rest of the immune system. The parasite molecules directly include the production of a low level of inflammatory cytokines; tumour necrosis factor (TNF-8) at this level the (TNF-V) is an anti-parasite, working together with an interferon to induce production of nitric oxide and other toxic radicals.

2.8 EPIDEMIOLOGY

The prevalence of malaria varies with different natural conditions; these include factors relating to the parasites. The vector (mosquitoes), environmental and climatic factor, human factor including the epidemiology of the diseases. Environmental factors such as temperature, humidity and rainfall are the most important among all. They however affect the life cycle and also the rate of development of the parasite (Sporagony), (Okeli 2014). Human factors such as agricultural occupation also have a great on malaria epidemiology

2.9 DIAGNOSIS

Worldwide microscopy remains the total choice for malaria diagnosis. In comparison to analysis of blood by polymerase chain reaction (PCR), microscopy is 85%-95% sensitive and 95%-100% specific microscopic examination of 10-100 parasites per microlitre of blood and microscopy permits species identification. Microscopy is however time-consuming and it requires sufficient operation of a microscope that has been used to identify malaria parasites. One of such assay is the quality blood control malaria test system; a sample of blood is mixed in a capillary tube. Although, it gives result more quickly than the traditional microscopy (preparing of sample may require up to 10 minutes). Moreover, species identification is highly problematic with assay. Therefore, in making comparison to thick and thin smear analysis, the (QBC) system is 70%-100% sensitive and 85%-95% specific.

2.10 PREVENTION AND CONTROL

The control of Anopheles mosquitoes is especially by the spraying of house and by so doing residual insecticides will reduce malaria risk greatly. However, unless eradication is completely on all visitors and non-immune residents should take regular prophylactic drugs, sleeping at night under mosquitoes which bites in the dark and may also reduce the likelihood of acquiring other mosquito or borne infections, proper drainage should be provided to avoid stagnant water where the vectors breed, multiply and infect their susceptible host (man).

2.10.1 Insecticide-Treated Nets (ITNs).

The wide-scale implementation of ITNs is now one of the strategies to reduce mobility from Malaria (WHO, 2013). The promotion and use of insecticides treated Mosquito nets have become a leading strategy in mosquito prevention and control. (Dike *et al.*, 2011). Surveys have shown a dramatic reduction in the number of cases of Malaria in communities using insecticide-treated Mosquito nets. Regular use of treated nets has been shown to reduce child mortality by about 25%. Children sleeping under treated net are less prone to anaemia malnutrition and Malaria. To

be most effective, Mosquito nets must be re-treated with recommended insecticides at least every six (6) months to give maximum protection. They also prevent the bite and stings of other insects.

2.10.2 Mosquito Coils

A cheap, popular way to prevent Mosquito bites is to burn Mosquito coils under tables or while sitting outside. Coils are made from pyrethrum, a powder derived from chrysanthemum plants, and burn slowly to provide protection for hours (AMCA, 2008).

2.10.3 Personal Protections

Wearing protective clothing such as long sleeves, shirts, socks and shoes, and insect repellent while outdoors reduce the bite (Burkett *et al.*, 2014). Some repellent formulations can be applied only to the skin or on both skin and clothing (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2008).

2.11 TREATMENT OF MALARIA

Treatment of malaria consists of mostly wide used drugs of choice for treating malaria, and these are: Chloroquine, but recently due to several reports of Chloroquine resistance, its synthesis Analgin, came into use. Other antimalarial drugs such as Fansider, Metakalfine, Halpen, Myloquine and Athesonate, (Ephraim, 2016).

Nigerian chemoprophylaxis in pregnant women, also anti-malarial drugs such as Mexoquine has been proved to be effective.

2.12 THE A B O BLOOD GROUP SYSTEM

The human first blood that was discovered is the A B O system which consists of four main blood groups which are the A B AB and O (Landstainer, 2010). And out of about twenty (20) blood groups in man.

The A B O system is of paramount importance for 150 antibodies are normally present on the plasma, these are determined by the antigens (coated on the surface of the Red Blood Cells (R B

Cs), antigens determinants escribed to possess the A and B, some individuals poises the antigens determinants and hence belong to group A, while others belong to group B and contain B determinants. There are other groups of the determinants who possess neither of the determinants and belong to group O. However another group of individuals possess antibodies in their serum, these are called 'natural occurring 'antibodies directed against its own erythrocytes. Thus, individuals of blood group A possess antisera B and those of group B possess antisera A and others having antisera A or B, these groups belong to blood group AB. This study leads to the understanding of the major blood groups of man especially the A, B, O system and self-recognition, which leads to the major blood group.

The blood group determination is based on the agglutination (clumping of blood) that is the Red Blood Cells and depends on the reaction of the agglutination (Antigen) on the R B Cs and the agglutination (antibodies). In some individuals, these antibodies may occur naturally and without any obvious antibodies in response to any parental administration of the foreign R B Cs antigen, especially during fetus and from a blood transfusion. Blood group antibodies can be classified based on the way they react with appropriate Red cells. Those in which they do not usually agglutinate carrying them and are suspended In a saline medium such as bounealbumia, these are called incomplete antibodies by Ford in 1973. In individuals who research the naturally occurring antibodies of the A B O system, exists in all individuals in which they are compatible. The blood groups involved are of fundamental importance for practical purposes, especially in blood transfusion. The rhesus (RL) is also important because of its antibodies that are easily induced as immune reactions although, they can rarely be found spontaneously immature. However, the complication of both A B O and the (RL) are therefore considerable. The selection of human subjects with a particular blood group by the female anopheles mosquito could lead to malaria infection in human blood. Certain authors found significant differences in the distribution among communities and geographical entities. However, the availability of data on the world

distribution of human blood showed that the O blood group has 62% whereas only 38% shared among other groups of A, B and AB (WHO, 2013).

This is significantly elicited that averagely sized out of every ten people in the population belong to the blood group O. Thus, under normal conditions of the free choice by the female anopheles mosquito could lead to blood group and malaria infection which was reviewed by Livingstone's in 2019. However, certain authors found a significant difference in the distribution of human blood. This reveals that 62% of the world population belongs to various communities and geographical entities. Therefore, available data on the world distribution of human blood showed that the O blood group has 62% whereby 38% is shared among others that is A, B and AB as mentioned earlier. The factor that led to the preferential feeding of Anopheles mosquito on blood group O remain under but certainly, this belief that there is a greater attraction towards blood group A B and AB. Where anopheles gambiense which gives the ratio of B A and AB as 5:4:3:3 '33%, 27%, 20% and 20% respectively (Awolola et al, 2013).

However, the female anopheles mosquito has a chance of feeding on the other blood group for their own survival. Blood group O predominates. No significant difference parasitically was selected between the groups but it is, therefore, possible that some differences exist at low level of transmission, for example, *Anopheles gambiense* towards various blood groups which produces parasitological differences (Awolola et al, 2013).

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 STUDY AREA

This study was carried out in Katsina Local Government Area (LGA), Katsina State, Northern Nigeria between October and December 2021. It borders Kaduna State to the South, Jigawa and Kano States to the East, Zamfara State to the West and the Niger Republic to the North. The State occupies an area of about 23,938sq kilometres. It is situated on Latitude between 11° 07' 49N' 13° 22' 57'' and Longitude 6° 52' 03E and 9° 9' 02'E". The major tribes in the State are Hausa and Fulani and Islam is the predominant religion. Languages spoken in the State are Hausa and Fulfulde. Rainfall is highest between June and October with mean daily temperature fluctuating between 20.6°C and 35.0°C, while dry season ranges between November and April when the daily maximum temperature exceeds 40.0°C. The markets situated in this LGA are found in Chake, Yar' Kutungu, Central Market, Yan Cefane, Tsohuwar Kasuwa, Yar'adua, Yan Kaji and Yan Katako among the others. The hospitals situated in this LGA are General Hospital, Federal Medical Center, Turai Maternity Hospital, Kofar Kaura Hospital among the others.

3.2 SAMPLING TECHNIQUES/ COLLECTION

Blood samples were collected from 100 patients visiting the General Hospital Katsina from October to December 2021. Several methods have been derived from selecting samples that will be representative of the population. These sampling techniques include the random sampling method applied in collecting data. This is because every member has the chance of being selected without specifying.

3.3 RAPID DIAGNOSTIC TESTS (RDT)

Rapid diagnostic test for malaria has the capability to detect 100 parasites from all Plasmodium species (WHO/ MAL, 2015).

3.3.1 PROCEDURE

A finger is punctured and the blood sample was collected using a dipstick/capillary tube, the blood dropped on the blood portion (B) of the kit and a buffer solution was added to the buffer position (A) the result was read after 10 minutes. Single line as negative and double line as a positive result.

3.4 THICK BLOOD FILM

A thick blood film is usually prepared before the thin film, since it is a rapid and sensitive method for the detection of malaria parasites when they are few in number, especially in mild infection. The Red Blood Cells (RBCs) are lysed during staining because they are not fixed. The parasites and the white cells are clearly seen. The film must be handled with care to prevent the blood from being washed away from the slide during staining.

3.4.1 PROCEDURE

A large drop of blood was placed on the edge of a slide with the edge of another slide and using a circular motion the blood was spread over an area of about two centimetres in diameter, it was continuously stirred for 30 seconds to prevent the formation of fibrin, which obscured, the parasite after staining then allowed to air dry stained with Giemsa stain, washed, dry and examined using oil emersion.

3.5 THIN FILM

A thin blood film is prepared from the same blood specimen and examined to identify the specific parasite seen in the thick films. In thin films, the blood cells are fixed and the characteristics features of the parasites are demonstrated. The size and shape of Red Cells are used to identify the various plasmodium species. Examination of thin films is significant in the identification of mixed infections (thin-film disc over's what species of *Plasmodium* caused the infection. Kathleen Romito., 2011).

3.5.1 PROCEDURE

A small drop of the same blood was placed at one end of a clean grease-free slide a spreader was used to spread the blood at an angle of 45 degrees the slide was moved backwards marking a thin film that was allowed to dry rapidly in the air and examined using oil emersion.

3.6 BLOOD GROUPING

ABO blood groups were typed by agglutination using commercial antisera (Biotech Laboratories LTD, Ipswich, and Suffolk, UK).

The two drops of whole blood were placed in two different places of a grease free slide on which the few drops of antisera for blood group A and B was applied. Antisera D was used to determine the Rhesus factor (RL), in A B O blood grouping.

3.6.1 PROCEDURE

One drop of anti-sera A and a drop of anti-sera B reagent separately were placed on a labelled a drop of 20% test suspension was added to each of the drops on the tile. It was then mixed using a clean stick and spread evenly on the tile over an area of 10-15mm millimetre in diameter the tile was tilted and left for two minutes and the result was recorded.

3.7 METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

The overall data was calculated. Chi-square comparisons between rates of parasite recovery and $P > 0.05$ were considered significant.

3.8 ETHICAL CLEARANCE

The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Katsina State Health Research Ethics Committee and accordingly by the Honorable Commissioner of Health.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 RESULT

Presented in Table 1 are data representing A B O blood groups with malaria parasitaemia infection densities distribution among patients attending General Hospital Katsina. A total of 100 blood samples made up of 20(20.00%) A Positive and 3(3.00%) A Negative, B Positive 34 (34.00%) and 3 (3.00%) B Negative, AB Positive 12 (12.00%) and 3 (3.00%) AB Negative and O Positive 25(25.00%) and O Negative of 1 (1.00%). There is no any significant association between malaria parasitaemia densities with A B O blood groups, since the calculated value at 95% ($P>0.05$) level of confidence is in males and 1.00 in females. The chi-square tabulated value is 7.81.

Table 1: The Distribution of Blood Groups in 100 Cases of Patients Attending General Hospital Katsina

Blood Groups	Positive(+)	Negative (-)	Column Total
A	20	3	23
B	34	2	36
AB	12	3	15
O	25	1	26
TOTALS	91	9	100

The result in table 1 above shows the number of occurrences of malaria parasite in different blood groups with the numbers are as follows A (23) B (36), AB (15), and O (26), which shows that B (36) having the highest number of occurrence with AB (15) having the least number of occurrence.

Table.2: Malaria Parasite Count in Four Different Blood Groups of Patients Attending General Hospital Katsina

Blood Groups/Parasite	Positive(+)	Negative (-)	Column Total
A	20.93	2.07	23
B	32.76	3.24	36
AB	13.65	1.35	15
O	23.66	2.34	26
TOTALS	91	9	100

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 DISCUSSION

The results obtained in this study showed that a total of 100 blood samples made up of 20(20.00%) A Positive and 3(3.00%) A Negative, B Positive 34 (34.00%) and 2 (2.00%) B Negative, AB Positive 12 (12.00%) and 3 (3.00%) AB Negative and O Positive 25(25.00%) and O Negative of 1 (1.00%). These findings showed that the most prevalent blood group is B with almost (40%) and the least, AB (6.823%). This was different from that of (Otajevw, 2013) which reported prevalence rates of malaria and blood group among students of Igbinedion University Okada as 4(3.9%), 16(15.4%), 32(30.8%) and 52 (50.0%) for AB, B, A and O in increasing order respectively. Data obtained in this study also showed that the most prevalent blood group is B because 36 patients represent almost 50% of the sample. At the other extreme, the least occurring group was AB (6.823%) with 12 patients. These findings are consistent with the earlier study by (Otajavwo, 2013) which reported AB with 4(3.9%) as the least occurring and differs from that of (Zerihum *et al* 2011) which recorded O with (51.3%) as the most occurring group. This differs because of ethnicity, racial and geographical differences of the study location. Further investigation revealed that 100% of the patients sampled harboured malaria parasites of various densities. This rather high parasitaemia rate suggests that patients visiting General Hospital Katsina are hyperendemic for malaria. Data obtained in this study also showed that the rate was observed in the B blood group with 36% severe (cases) densities of *plasmodium falciparum* parasites infection. These findings disagree with that of Ilozumba and Uzozie (2009) which recorded 100% malaria parasitaemia among blood group AB individuals followed by 94.9% among blood group O, it also disagrees with the work of Tekeste and Petros (2010) that severe malaria cases are common among patient of blood group A, B, AB and less in blood o

with 25(35.7%), 16(22.9%), 15(21.4%) and 14(20.0%) respectively. It is noted that blood groups A, AB and O showed 24(0.044%), 12(6.823%) and 28(1.502%) respectively also showed some level of malaria densities. Although a study using a larger sample size would be required to validate these findings, it seems there is a relative spread of malaria parasitaemia across all blood groups in this study. This is consistent with findings from a study carried out by Fischer and Boone (2016) in which they reported that malaria occurs in patients of any blood group, that no particular blood group precludes the possibility of severe malaria. Data obtained showed that among the adults and children (teenage) groups starting from the age of zero. Children showed the highest percentage of 78% and less 22% in adults. Children of blood group B showed the highest malaria parasitaemia with 30(28.08%) and 6(7.92%) in adults, blood group O with 20(21.84%) in teenagers and 8(6.16%) in adults. Blood group A with 19(18.72%) in children and 5(5.28%) in adults and AB with 9(9.36%) in children and 3(2.64%) in adults. Also, going by sex distribution of malaria parasitaemia, results revealed that much more female patients were infected with malaria parasites compared to the male patients. This does not tally with the suggestion of (Portilo and Sullivan 2017) that genetic factors could play a role by endowing females with immune-regulatory potentials to cope better with some diseases. Again, the occurrence of a higher malaria parasitaemia rate among the female patients across all blood groups is because the female and children are vulnerable to malaria attacks.

5.2 CONCLUSION

The results of the study conducted on 100 blood samples collected were found to be positive with Plasmodium species, which shows that different blood groups have different susceptibility patterns for malaria infection. According to this study, blood group B had the highest (36) susceptibility of malaria infection, followed by group O (26) and A (23) then AB group (15) with the least infection and severity. In all, there is no significant relationship between the malaria parasite and blood groups. Since the P-value = 7.81 > 0.05. The low infectivity rate recorded in

this study suggests that a little effort will certainly crash the prevalence rate of mosquito-related disease.

5.3 RECOMMENDATION

Having considered malaria in different blood groups among patients attending General Hospital Katsina.

- It is recommended that findings in this study should be reviewed using a much larger sample size.
- Consequently, available malaria prophylactic and therapeutic strategies by health agencies should be directed at individuals of all groups without any discrimination or preference for a particular group.
- Good environmental management which includes the construction of sloppy gutters to allow free flow of water is very important in reducing breeding sites.
- The use of long-lasting insecticide nets (LLINS) effectively especially to the under 5 age groups who are both susceptible and act as a good reservoir host for the gametocyte stage could be very important in reducing the scourge.
- There should be free supply of long-lasting insecticide nets (LLINS) at maternity and ensure that they are utilized effectively.
- Government should provide free medication until one is certified-free from Malaria disease.

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APPENDIX I

Figure 1

Figure 2

APPENDIX II

KATSINA STATE GOVERNMENT OF NIGERIA

Received from MUSA ABUBAKAR IBRAHIM
the sum of THREE THOUSAND
being Documents for Ethical Review ^{only} FREE ^{for the year 2021}

Printed By: The Government Printer, Katsina

ORIGINAL

Signature or mark of payee: _____
Signature of witness to mark: _____
Occupation and address of witness: _____

Signature of Revenue Collector: Abdullahi
Date: 26-10-2021
Department: Accounting
Station: W/D

REVENUE COLLECTOR'S RECEIPT
KTTA/20569120
FOR ₦ 3,000.00
HEAD NO. 152100100100
SUB-HEAD NO. 12020430
TITLE ETHICAL REVIEW FEES

Plate 1: Ethical Clearance Receipt

MINISTRY OF HEALTH KATSINA STATE

Tel: Hon. Commissioner 065-434537 (DL)
434518 (DL)

State Secretariat Complex,
I.B.B. Way Dandagoro
P.M.B. 2075, Katsina.

Permanent Secretary 065-34554

Our Ref: MOH/ADM/SUB/1152/1/602

Date: 26th October 2021

Your Ref: _____

602

KATSINA STATE HEALTH RESEARCH ETHICAL REVIEW COMMITTEE (HREC) FULL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

Re: "THE EFFECT OF MALARIA AMONG PATIENTS WITH DIFFERENT BLOOD GROUP ATTENDING GENERAL
HOSPITAL KATSINA"

Katsina HREC assigned number	-MOH/ADM/SUB/1152/1/602
Name of principal investigator	- MUSA ABUBAKAR IBRAHIM
Address of Principal Investigator	- Biological Sciences Dept, Al-Qalam University Katsina.
Date of receipt of Valid Application	- 21 st /1 0/ 2021
Date of HREC meeting and Approval	-26 th /10/2021

This is to inform you that the research described in the submitted protocol, the consent forms and other participants information materials have been reviewed and given **Approval** by the Katsina State Health Research Ethics Committee and accordingly by the Honorable Commissioner of Health.

Please note: this approval dates from 26th /10/2021 to 25th/10/2022. No recruitment of participant into this research may be conducted outside these dates.

All informed consent forms in this study must carry the Katsina HREC assigned number and the duration of the Katsina HREC approval for the study.

If there is a delay in starting the research, please inform the Katsina HREC so that starting date can be adjusted accordingly.

No changes are permitted to the research without prior approval by the Katsina HREC except in circumstances outlined in the national code of health research ethics. <http://www.nhrec.net>

Katsina HREC reserves the right to conduct a compliance assessment to your research site without prior notification.

Dr Ma'awuya Aliu,
Director Public Health,
Chairman, Katsina HREC.
+234 7088365997

"Home of Heritage and Hospitality"

Plate 2: Ethical Clearance

Plate 3:RDT Cassete

Plate 4: Grease Free Slide

Table 3: Chi-Square Relative Distribution between the two variables

Blood Group	O	E	(O-E)	(O-E) ²	$\frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$	$\sum_E \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$
A	20	20.93	-0.93	0.86	0.04	
B	34	32.76	1.24	1.53	0.04	
AB	12	13.65	-1.65	2.72	0.19	
O	25	23.66	1.34	1.79	0.07	
					Total	X ² = 0.34

Key : E=Expected value, O=Observed value

The degree of freedom = (Columns-1)(Rows -1)

$$(2-1) (4-1)= 1 \times 3= 3$$

$$p = 0.05$$

Percentage Points of the Chi-Square Distribution

Degrees of Freedom	Probability of a larger value of χ^2								
	0.99	0.95	0.90	0.75	0.50	0.25	0.10	0.05	0.01
1	0.000	0.004	0.016	0.102	0.455	1.32	2.71	3.84	6.63
2	0.020	0.103	0.211	0.575	1.386	2.77	4.61	5.99	9.21
3	0.115	0.352	0.584	1.212	2.366	4.11	6.25	7.81	11.34
4	0.297	0.711	1.064	1.923	3.357	5.39	7.78	9.49	13.28
5	0.554	1.145	1.610	2.675	4.351	6.63	9.24	11.07	15.09
6	0.872	1.635	2.204	3.455	5.348	7.84	10.64	12.59	16.81
7	1.239	2.167	2.833	4.255	6.346	9.04	12.02	14.07	18.48
8	1.647	2.733	3.490	5.071	7.344	10.22	13.36	15.51	20.09
9	2.088	3.325	4.168	5.899	8.343	11.39	14.68	16.92	21.67
10	2.558	3.940	4.865	6.737	9.342	12.55	15.99	18.31	23.21
11	3.053	4.575	5.578	7.584	10.341	13.70	17.28	19.68	24.72
12	3.571	5.226	6.304	8.438	11.340	14.85	18.55	21.03	26.22
13	4.107	5.892	7.042	9.299	12.340	15.98	19.81	22.36	27.69
14	4.660	6.571	7.790	10.165	13.339	17.12	21.06	23.68	29.14
15	5.229	7.261	8.547	11.037	14.339	18.25	22.31	25.00	30.58
16	5.812	7.962	9.312	11.912	15.338	19.37	23.54	26.30	32.00
17	6.408	8.672	10.085	12.792	16.338	20.49	24.77	27.59	33.41
18	7.015	9.390	10.865	13.675	17.338	21.60	25.99	28.87	34.80
19	7.633	10.117	11.651	14.562	18.338	22.72	27.20	30.14	36.19
20	8.260	10.851	12.443	15.452	19.337	23.83	28.41	31.41	37.57
22	9.542	12.338	14.041	17.240	21.337	26.04	30.81	33.92	40.29
24	10.856	13.848	15.659	19.037	23.337	28.24	33.20	36.42	42.98
26	12.198	15.379	17.292	20.843	25.336	30.43	35.56	38.89	45.64
28	13.565	16.928	18.939	22.657	27.336	32.62	37.92	41.34	48.28
30	14.953	18.493	20.599	24.478	29.336	34.80	40.26	43.77	50.89
40	22.164	26.509	29.051	33.660	39.335	45.62	51.80	55.76	63.69
50	27.707	34.764	37.689	42.942	49.335	56.33	63.17	67.50	76.15
60	37.485	43.188	46.459	52.294	59.335	66.98	74.40	79.08	88.38